

SystemVerilog Scheduling Semantics

Ali Adel Mahdi

Abstract—SystemVerilog simulation tools use a stratified event scheduler. Determining when signal updates and observations occur depends on how procedural and continuous assignments are ordered across the simulation time slot regions. This paper shows an overview of these regions and clarifies their roles, which helps avoid race conditions and ensures predictable interactions between design and testbench components.

Keywords—SystemVerilog, event scheduling, simulation semantics, assertion sampling, UVM

I. INTRODUCTION

Digital simulator tools model hardware behavior over a discrete time slot which is the basic unit of simulation time, within a slot the simulator orders reads, writes, sampling, and checks to produce deterministic results. This ordering is defined by a stratified event scheduler which divides each time slot into multiple regions serving three main purposes: executing design code, driving verification activity and sampling/evaluating concurrent assertions.

By knowing how the event scheduler works, you can avoid common race conditions, for example the read-after-write (RAW) race, which occurs when both statements use blocking assignments: one statement writes a variable while another reads that same variable within the same time slot. Because multiple active processes can execute in any order within the same region the reader can observe either the old or the new value this nondeterminism is considered a race condition. Within a single time step the simulator executes the regions in a defined sequence (active, inactive, nonblocking-assignment update/NBA, etc.). If both the reading and the writing occur in the active region, the observed result depends on which statement runs first. To prevent this race, we use nonblocking assignments for sequential logic so write operations are scheduled to the NBA region after all active regions read operations have completed.

II. SYSTEMVERILOG EVENT REGIONS

The SystemVerilog event scheduler defines the ordering of design and testbench activity within a single simulation time slot by dividing the time slot into multiple regions with different purposes. Simulation proceeds through the main regions which are (preponed, active, inactive, non-blocking assignment (NBA), observed, reactive, re-inactive, re-NBA, and postponed), while Programming Language Interface (PLI) control points regions (e.g., pre-active, pre-/post-NBA, pre-/post-Observed, pre-/post-re-NBA, and pre-postponed) allow external C/C++ routines written by the users to observe or influence state at well-defined boundaries.¹

This regions ordering ensures that concurrent assertions can sample before updates and evaluate after the design stabilizes and that verification code can react without racing the design. The overall flow of these regions within a time slot is summarized as shown in Fig. 1 [4], [9].

1- Preponed region

At the very start of the time slot before any value changes take effect the simulator provides a snapshot of design so that concurrent assertions can take their samples.

Clocking-block inputs with *#Istep* skew are captured to ensure that later updates in the time slot do not affect what was sampled [3].

2- Pre-active region

This is a PLI control point that occurs just before the active region, it allows callback C/C++ routines written by the users to read and write values and to schedule work that must occur before the evaluation performed in the active.

3- Active region

Procedural module code executes, blocking assignments update immediately, continuous assignments and primitives are evaluated here, and the right-hand sides of non-blocking assignments are computed with their left-hand updates scheduled for NBA region to avoid race conditions. Some system tasks such as *\$display* and *\$finish* execute here as well [1].

4- Inactive region

Work explicitly scheduled by *#0* runs after all active work completes but before non-blocking updates are applied.

5- Pre-NBA region

A PLI control point that occurs just before the non-blocking region.

6- NBA region

All left-hand sides of non-blocking assignments scheduled for the current slot are updated together here [8].

7- Post-NBA region

A PLI control point that follows the NBA region commonly used to observe the post-commit state.

8- Pre-Observed region

A PLI control point just before assertions are evaluated. It allows reading stabilized values after active/NBA effects with restrictions on writes to prepare for property evaluation.

9- Observed region

Concurrent assertions are evaluated using the samples taken in preponed region, clocking-block inputs with explicit *#0 skew* are also sampled here so that property evaluation reflects a stable design [5], [7].

10- Post-Observed region

A PLI control point immediately after assertion evaluation is used to review property outcome.

11- Reactive region

Testbench/program and checker code execute here, including assertion action blocks (pass/fail code), blocking assignments in program blocks and RHS of program-side non-blocking assignments are evaluated with their updates scheduled for Re-NBA [2], [6].

12- Re-Inactive region

Zero-delay (*#0*) deferrals scheduled from reactive/program code are executed at this point.

¹ Note here that the Programming Language Interface (PLI) allows user's C/C++ routines to observe simulation behavior through event regions. While the Direct Programming Interface (DPI) provides a simple way to call C/C++ functions from SystemVerilog code without changing the simulator scheduling.

13- Pre-Re-NBA region

A PLI control point immediately before the reactive non-blocking update phase to provide the same job as pre-NBA but for the reactive set.

14- Re-NBA region

Left-hand sides of non-blocking assignments scheduled from reactive/program code are committed together and clocking-block outputs with explicit #0 skew are also driven here [4].

15- Post-Re-NBA region

A PLI control point that follows the re-NBA commits to allow inspection of the final reactive updates.

16- Pre-Postponed region

A PLI control point after all iterative regions have completed and just before the postponed region.

17- Postponed region

The final region of the time slot, \$monitor and \$strobe execute here and functional coverage is sampled here also, no new value changes are permitted and the simulation tool advances to the next time slot.

Figure 1: Event scheduling regions

III. ILLUSTRATIVE EXAMPLE: VISIBILITY ACROSS REGIONS IN ONE TIME SLOT

We can consider a tiny example: a flip-flop a toggled with a non-blocking assignment at each rising clock edge as shown in Sample 1 and an observer prints once in active, once after a zero-delay in inactive and once in the postponed region using \$strobe system task. So the simulation time remains fixed and we change only the region of observation within the same time slot.

At the first rising edge the active print shows the pre-commit value of a because the non-blocking update has not taken effect yet and also the #0 print in inactive is pre-commit and you will notice it prints the same value. In postponed region which is after the NBA region the \$strobe system task reports the final value. The waveform in Fig. 2 shows toggling after NBA, and Table I shows the observations at each rising edge with the three regions [2].

Sample 1: mini_regions.sv — NBA commit after edge

```
// Timescale 1 ns/1 ns
bit clk=0, a=0;
initial forever #5 clk = ~clk;
always_ff @(posedge clk) a <= ~a;
always @(posedge clk) begin
    $display("%0t ACTIVE a=%0b", $time, a);
    #0 $display("%0t INACTIVE a=%0b", $time, a);
end
always @(posedge clk) $strobe("%0t POSTPONED a=%0b", $time, a);
```

Figure 2: mini_regions.sv waveform

TABLE I. MINI_REGIONS OBSERVATIONS

Time (ns)	Region	a	Reason
5	active	0	$a <= \sim a$ not committed yet
5	inactive	0	Still before NBA
5	postponed	1	NBA committed in this slot
15	active	1	Previous commit visible
15	inactive	1	Still before NBA
15	postponed	0	Next commit applied

Timescale 1 ns/1 ns, output captured from mini_regions.sv

IV. PROGRAM BLOCKS VS. MODULE BLOCKS IN TESTBENCH SCHEDULING

In SystemVerilog both module and program blocks can contain testbench code, but they differ in their scheduling semantics. A module is a general-purpose container, it can contain RTL or verification code and its procedural blocks (initial, always, always_ff, always_comb, etc.) execute in the active region of the simulator's event scheduler. While a program block is designed specifically for testbench-level control and scheduled after the design's activity to prevent many race conditions between stimulus and the DUV (design under verification) and to achieve this all statements in a program execute in the reactive region which follows the observed region where the DUV's results have already executed and stabilized.

Because of this later scheduling constructs such as always blocks are disallowed in program blocks, the always procedural block belongs to the active region semantics which reacts continuously to events in parallel with the design which can violate the ordering guarantee that testbench code must never race design activity. SystemVerilog makes this clear it enforces this separation by permitting always only in modules and similar design-oriented blocks [10].

Verification engineers use an initial block combined with a forever loop as shown in Sample 2 to create the equivalent always block behavior inside a program block.

Sample 2: *apb4_tb.sv* — program block

```

program apb4_tb;
  initial forever begin
    send_apb4_packet ();
  end
endprogram

```

It behaves similarly to an always block but more importantly it executes in the reactive region, maintaining the correct separation between stimulus and DUV activity. Although many verification frameworks now rely on classes and the UVM which have similar protections internally.

V. UVM INTERACTIONS WITH THE EVENT SCHEDULER

The Universal Verification Methodology (UVM) operates within the SystemVerilog simulation semantics and it does not replace the stratified event scheduler but instead builds an abstraction layer over it. Each UVM component executes as procedural code mapped to the event scheduler's existing regions.

UVM drivers generate signal-level activity through clocking blocks at the lowest level and when using a clocking block it defines an input sampling event and an output driving event which associated with a specific clock edge negedge/posedge, so during simulation these correspond to multiple regions.

- a) Inputs sampled with a *#1step* skew are captured in the preponed region, before any design updates.
- b) Inputs with zero skew are sampled in the observed region, after active and NBA updates [5].
- c) Outputs with zero skew driven in the re-NBA region.

The sequencing showed above by the SystemVerilog event scheduler guarantees that stimulus generation and DUV response never overlap within the same region which helps avoid racing conditions.

UVM's phase mechanism is not tied to SystemVerilog scheduling regions, it is a framework of method calls executed during simulation. The default configuration is that all UVM phases run in the active region of the SystemVerilog event scheduler when the top-level testbench is a module, unless the top-level testbench that calls *uvm_pkg::run_test()* is defined as a program block, which causes the execution to occur in the reactive region [11].

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper presented the SystemVerilog stratified event scheduler and illustrated its behavior with a tiny practical example and the resulting picture is simple ordering is deterministic across regions yet intentionally unspecified among independent processes within a region. Which explains common hazards such as read-after-write races in the active region.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Huge thanks to the members of the VLSI community for their continuous shared insights and valuable feedback that inspired the ideas presented in this paper.

REFERENCES

- [1] Shanthi V A, "SystemVerilog event scheduler," *Maven Silicon Blog*, Feb. 1, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://maven-blogs-admin.maven-silicon.com/systemverilog-event-scheduler>.
- [2] Kiran, "Scheduling semantics," *24x7FPGA – SV Verification Directory*, Jan. 14, 2025. [Online]. Available: https://24x7fpga.com/sv_directory/2025_01_14_scheduling_semantics.
- [3] "SystemVerilog scheduling semantics," *VLSI Verify*, n.d. [Online]. Available: <https://vlsiverify.com/systemverilog/systemverilog-scheduling-semantics>.
- [4] IEEE Standards Association, *IEEE Standard for SystemVerilog—Unified Hardware Design, Specification, and Verification Language (IEEE Std 1800-2017)*, Feb. 22, 2018. [Online]. Available: https://rfsoc.mit.edu/6S965/_static/F24/documentation/1800-2017.pdf.
- [5] "SystemVerilog clocking blocks," *ChipVerify*, n.d. [Online]. Available: <https://www.chipverify.com/systemverilog/systemverilog-clocking-blocks>.
- [6] "Verilog scheduling semantics," *ChipVerify*, n.d. [Online]. Available: <https://www.chipverify.com/verilog/verilog-scheduling-semantics>.
- [7] "Event semantics of SystemVerilog," *The Octet Institute*, n.d. [Online]. Available: <https://www.theoctetinstitute.com/content/sv/event-semantics>.
- [8] "Scheduling regions in SystemVerilog," *VLSI Worlds*, n.d. [Online]. Available: <https://vlsiworlds.com/system-verilog/scheduling-regions-in-system-verilog>.
- [9] "SystemVerilog scheduling semantics," *Verification Guide*, n.d. [Online]. Available: <https://verificationguide.com/systemverilog/systemverilog-scheduling-semantics>.
- [10] "SystemVerilog program block," *ChipVerify*, n.d. [Online]. Available: <https://www.chipverify.com/systemverilog/systemverilog-program-block>.
- [11] Verification Academy, "UVM runtime phases," *UVM Reference*, n.d. [Online]. Available: https://verificationacademy.com/verification-methodology-reference/uvm/docs_1.2/html/files/base/uvm_runtime_phases-svh.html.